

Arab Life Matters: Gaza Genocide and Political Dissent among Arab Diasporas in the West

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Religionized Apartheid, Fake Knowledge and Disproportionate Death Tolls During Gaza Genocide

The Gulf War left some Arabs feeling proud that Saddam Hussein has attacked Israel and stood up to the West. It also left many feeling humiliated and resentful of the West's military presence in the Persian Gulf, the West's overwhelming military dominance, and their apparent inability to shape their own destiny. ... Some openings in Arab political systems have already occurred. The principal beneficiaries of these openings have been Islamist movements. In the Arab world, in short, Western democracy strengthens anti-Western political forces. (Huntington 1996, p. 32)

In his well-known book *The Clash of Civilizations*, Samuel Huntington argues that in the post-cold war new world 'the great divisions among mankind and the dominating source of conflict will be cultural' and that 'the principal conflicts of global politics will occur between nations and groups of different civilizations' (p. 22). Huntington defines a civilization as 'the highest cultural grouping of people and the broadest level of cultural identity people have, short of that which distinguishes humans from other species' (p. 24). According to the above-mentioned quotation from *The Clash of Civilizations*, Islamic civilization is the new enemy of the Western civilization. Huntington argues that the conflict along the fault line between Western and Islamic civilizations has been going on for 1,300 years. Even though Huntington identifies major seven or eight civilizations of Western, Confucian, Japanese, Islamic, Hindu, Slavic-Orthodox, Latin American, and possibly African civilization (p. 29), Islamic civilization stood out as the most dangerous, with its different values and Islamist fundamentalists. Huntington not only inconsistently compares Islamic civilization with Western, when it should be Islamic versus Christian, or Eastern versus Western, but also complacently deters from describing American-led wars in the Middle East as colonial, and imperialist. He intentionally dismisses the fact that the Ottoman empire, like the British Empire, or the French Empire, or the American empire, are political imperialist projects that use religions or specific ideologies such as democracy as war propaganda.

Huntington's vision of the current world order and civilizational conflicts seems consistent with western politics and neocolonialism, and their eurocentric, Islamophobic and biased attitudes towards the Others, particularly Muslim others. American and western missions, and interferences in the Middle East are neocolonial wars meant to control oil, and resources in these countries, and to expand American hegemony. Populations in Muslim and Arab countries are resentful of the West's military presence in their region because of the huge human cost, damage, economic corruption, and political chaos and autocracy that resulted from what Huntington calls western *democratizing wars*. Western and American authorities have been allies and supporters of autocratic Arab rulers and their police states that systematically weaken and target opposition parties, and civilian dissent, but also, they disregard human rights in their wars in the Middle East. For example, during the Gulf War in 1991, Iraqi land, and infrastructure, including water plants and hospitals, were intentionally destroyed by the coalition forces led by American forces. Iraqi people, particularly women and children were starved, displaced, and killed. In 2003, Anglo-American forces killed about two million Iraqi civilians under the pretext of building democracy. Despite the huge global demonstrations against the American invasion of Iraq, and the reliable reports that Iraq did not possess weapons of mass destruction, America pursued its colonialist, destructive plan in Iraq that has been experiencing a civil war, insta-

bility and violence since 2003 to the present. America repeated its militarist invasions in Afghanistan with thousands of afghani civilians killed, and displaced, when Taliban fundamentalists resealed power in the country after 20 years of American rule. During the Syrian civil war (2012-2014), Syrian civilians and their land became a playground for experimenting with American and Russians weapons. Western and specifically American authorities weaponized Islamist groups to fight regimes in Syria and Iraq, as they did before with Bin Laden in his fight against Russians (Arnove 2003; Davis 2005; Dawisha 2009; Crawford 2015).

Furthermore, Huntington asserted that 'civilizations are dynamic, they rise and fall, they divide and merge and disappear' (p. 25). The Islamic empire or civilization fell centuries ago. Islamic states now are divided, and weak. So, why is the Islamic civilization a potential enemy to the west? The current Israeli war in Palestine and Lebanon can provide an answer. Huntington excludes the Jewish civilization symbolized in the state of Israel, and integrates it with western civilization, even though Israel is based in the Middle East. In *Orientalism*, Edward Said argues convincingly that 'one specifically American contribution to the discourse of empire is the specialized jargon of policy expertise' (p. xvi). For Said, there is a repeated pattern and an internal consistency of Orientalism as a system of knowledge and its ideas about the Orient or the East as career despite or beyond any

correspondence, or lack thereof, with a "real" Orient. Spreading distorted, politicized and biased knowledge based on preconceptions, and stereotypes of others has been a crucial tool of western imperial expansion. Said mentioned how bookstores in the US were filled with 'shabby screeds bearing screaming headlines about Islam and terror, Islam exposed, the Arab threat and the Muslim menace, all of them written by political polemicists pretending to knowledge imparted to them and others by experts who have supposedly penetrated to the heart of these strange Oriental peoples' (p. xvi). World, and American media, such as CNNs and Foxs, websites, huge numbers of evangelical and right-wing radio hosts, innumerable tabloids and middle-brow journalists reuse and re-cycle the same unverifiable knowledge and vast generalizations to motivate America against the foreign enemies, and terrorists in Iraq, Afghanistan, and different parts of the Middle East.

Fake knowledge and false propaganda have been systematic tools of all imperialist projects, including the current Israeli Zionist imperialist project in Palestine and the Middle East. Before and during the 1948-ethnic cleansing of Palestinians, Israelis and their western supporters claimed that Palestine is a land without a people, for a people without a land. In 1917, 96 % of Palestinian Arabs lived in Palestine, and 4 % were Jewish, but Balfour Declaration promised Jews the land of Palestine. The Zionist project was propagated as a redemption of the Western burden of the holocaust and western abuses against Jews. The Jewish diaspora was an essen-

tial component of the state of Israel. The new Jewish immigrants from Europe who were seen as a formerly oppressed minority became the majority. The state of Israel is also the state of Jewish people which ‘consists not only of the people residing in Israel but also of the Jews in the Diaspora’ (Chomsky, 1999, p. 282). The politics of Jewish diaspora is exceptional in the modern human history. Jews in the west actively support Israel as a substitute home. Jewish diaspora is, however, sustained by afflicting mass murders, like the Deir Yassin massacre, pain and trauma on millions of Palestinians whose diaspora is still unaccommodated. In 1967, Arabs lost more land to Israel that colonized Sinai, Golan heights, West Bank, and Gaza Strip. The USA’s global hegemony, and its political economy in the Middle East perfectly harmonize with Israel’s colonial project in the region. The USA-sponsored peace agreements between Israel and Egypt after the 1973 war, and then between Israel and Jordan, have changed the Arab-Israeli conflict. Through the Oslo accord (1993), Palestinians acknowledged the legitimacy of the state of Israel, even when Israelis refused the two-state solution.

Present Absentees: Palestinian Bodies are never Counted and Palestinian Diaspora never Ends

Palestinians are referred to as ‘present absentees.’ In all Arab countries, except for Jordan, Palestinians are given special cards identifying them as ‘Palestinian refugees’ and in all host countries, they are always aliens (Said 1993; Guergues 2024). The complete forgetfulness of

the rights of the Palestinian diasporas, and refugees who have been fighting for the right of return since 1948 severely contradicts not only with the advantaged position of Jewish diasporas, and the global celebration of their suffering, but also with the current Ukrainian diaspora that, unlike the Palestinian resistance and diaspora, is celebrated and supported by the west in their fight against Russian aggression. The current wars in Ukraine and the occupied territories of Palestine can be seen, then, as outcomes of global political fundamentalist structures that divide the world across antagonistic, prejudiced and imperialist lines. The democratic, civilized US, Europe, Israel and Ukraine versus the autocratic Russia, China, the Middle East and third world countries. In practicing their democracy, however, the western political elites undignifiedly show their hypocrisy, racism and double standards. When Ukrainians sought the right to join the NATO, that is against Russian national security, they received all political, military, and sociocultural support from European and American authorities and populations, yet the Palestinian genocide was totally ignored. Not only are international legal structures and human rights organizations undermined but the basic rights of freedom of speech and criticism are repressed as well. Israeli propaganda dominates, while opposite opinions and anti-genocide thinkers and activists are attacked and marginalized in media. Antisemitism becomes a ready accusation to silence any form of political or human criticism of Israel. Russia faced harsh economic and po-

litical sanctions, but nothing is done when Israeli ambassador shreds the UN charter. Israeli officials humiliate and attack the UN secretary general Antonio Guterres, kill UNRWA workers, and Israel disrespects all humanitarian laws and commits war crimes by mass murdering civilians, and blocking food, medicine, fuel, and tents from entering Gaza, while western and Arab countries remain silent.

In 1998, Noam Chomsky warned that Israel is emerging as “Judeo-Nazi” and “neo Nazi” state which wants “to kill as many Arabs as necessary, to deport them, to expel, to burn them, to make [them] hated by all, to make the ground unstable beneath the feet of the Jews in the Diaspora so that they shall be forced to rush here crying” (p. 753). In September 2023, Netanyahu delivered a speech to the United Nations General Assembly in New York during which he presented a map of ‘The New Middle East’ without Palestine. When Israel was normalizing relations with an increasing number of Arab countries, including Saudi Arabia, and claimed that the Abraham Accords will achieve peace in the region, Israeli extremist leadership under Netanyahu, his government and the Likud party have been fundamentalizing Israelis with ultra-nationalist Zionist dream of building the Greater Israel which will include Palestine, Lebanon, Syria, part of Iraq, Saudi Arabia and Sinia in Egypt (MEE 2023; Abdo 2024; Bulut 2024). Palestinians exist inside Palestine, in exile and in camps across Arab countries. The

whole world has witnessed massacres against Palestinians refugees in Sabra and Shatila in Lebanon, have seen the unarmed Palestinians in the occupied territories revolt against Israeli armed oppression, and its apartheid system of the 500 check points in Gaza and the West Bank Barrier. Peaceful objections during the first intifada (1987-1993), and the second intifada (2000), were met with Israeli bullets and international disregard.

The shameful, weak Arab stance, and their abandonment of Palestinians to be manipulated by Iranians, and the fundamentalist attitudes expressed by Netanyahu and his strident ministers, and their extremist supporters left Palestinian resistance movements with very limited options. They needed to fight for their land, and for the recognition of their denied rights. The Israeli war propaganda and its circulation of fake news after Hamas attack on the 7 October 2023 can be seen as the perfect incarnation of American-western uses of Islamophobia as a tool of chaos and colonialism in the region. It also signifies a historic turn in Israel's imperialist project, in American internal social security narratives and in international power relations. Hamas declared that the 7 October attack was meant to take Israeli hostages to exchange them with imprisoned Palestinians, including women and children. Hamas also claimed that the violent interference of the Israeli Defense Forces (IDF) by activating the Hannibal Directive during the attack led to the huge numbers of civilian victims (Smith 2024; Yaniv

2024). Even though Hamas committed a huge mistake by killing civilians and taking civilian hostages during the 7 October attack, Israel seized the golden chance to speed its imperialist project of Greater Israel. With its international immunity, relations and lobbies, Israel employed international media to victimize itself. Israeli authorities claimed that 1,139 people were killed and about 250 were taken hostages during the 7 October attack. Hamas fighters were accused of abhorrent behaviour of raping women and beheading children which were denied by Hamas. When no single evidence was provided of beheaded children (only two children died during 7 October Hamas attack. One child with a bullet, and the other died in hospital), Israeli and western media still circulated this fake information to dehumanize Palestinians (Chance, et al. 2023).

Female bodies and sexuality are essential parts of war and imperialist propaganda. Americans launched the Afghani and Iraqi wars to save women in the two countries from oppressive dictators and Islamists. In this sense, Israel is no exception. In June 2024, the UN released an in-depth investigative report which found that both Hamas and Israel had committed sexual violence and intentionally attacked civilians (p. 1). Yet, the report reveals that Israeli authorities obstructed the investigations and that the commission was unable to verify testimony of rape, could not get access to witnesses and crime scenes, and found no evidence that Hamas fighters inflicted or

were ordered to commit sexual violence. It also found some Israeli allegations to be contradictory, or false (UN Committee 2024). Likewise, other detailed investigative reports produced by highly respected institutions concluded that Israel's claims about sexual assaults did not stand up to scrutiny, and that alleged confessions of sexual violence were likely extracted under torture, and should not be accepted as credible evidence, and should not be published (UN Committee 2024; Robertson 2024; Graham-Harrison, et al. 2024; MEE 2024; Borger 2024; Human Rights Watch 2024; Amnesty International 2024; Physicians for Human Rights Israel 2024). Setting the media scene for its planned genocide, Israeli leadership employed typical imperialist stereotypes, and racist, Islamophobic narratives. Israel declared war on Hamas fighters who were described as 'terrorists' and are compared to 'Nazis', and 'ISIS'. Israeli Prime Minister Netanyahu was adamant to employ figurative and religious language to demonize and dehumanize Hamas: 'Hamas is ISIS. And we will defeat it just like the enlightened world defeated ISIS. This vile enemy wanted war, and it will get war' (Tharoor 2023; Reutersa 2023). Figurative religious language reminiscent of the Christian civilizing colonial missions was systematically used to falsify international public consciousness and to convince the dominantly white 'civilized' West that Israel's war with Hamas is an existential war against 'forces of darkness' and 'animalism', with Israel and the 'civilized' world characterized as 'forces of light' and 'humanity'. American, and

European political leaders and Zionist-oriented media echo Netanyahu's hate speech and support his collective punishment of Gazans by repeatedly stating that 'Israel has the right to defend itself.' Hamas fighters disappeared in tunnels, and Palestinian civilians were targeted.

In its battles against Hamas, Israel killed more than 43,600 people in Gaza, mostly civilians, and the majority of them were women and children. About 15,000 Palestinians are missing under the rubble (Saric 2024; Graham-Harrison 2024; Batrawy 2024). Sophia Stamatopoulou-Robbins focuses on the indirect deaths in Gaza and the West Bank that are equally shocking and appalling. Stamatopoulou-Robbins indicates that estimated deaths from Starvation are 62,413, and estimated deaths from lack of access to care for chronic diseases are 5,000. There is no data on estimated deaths from infectious diseases, maternal/neonatal and others (2024, p. 3-4). The disproportionate death toll between Israeli and Palestinian casualties is indicative of a repeated modern history of western colonialism where Arab and Muslim lives do not matter. French colonizers killed about a million and half Algerian, Italians raped and killed thousands of Libyan women, and men, and the American atrocities in the Abu Gharib prison speak of a sustained Western pattern of racism and colonial atrocities. As pictures, confirmed reports and videos documenting Israeli atrocities, and war crimes in Gaza including starving of civilians, attacking hospitals, destroying infrastructure,

and sexual violations and torture of Palestinian prisoners are dismissed in an unprecedented way, Israeli imperialism insidiously and insolently employed parts of the Talmud to religionize and justify their atrocities (Middle East Eye 2024; Litvin 2023). Even as on 21 November 2024, the International Court of Justice issued an arrest warrant against Netanyahu and Galant for committing war crimes in occupied Palestine, on 28 November 2024, the Vice-President of the European Commission, Joseph Borel asked Israeli people to fight 'mental colonization' and to work for peace. The genocide in Gaza and the displacement of about two million Shias in Lebanon are totally excused by the USA as Israel has the right to defend itself. The USA, Hungary and other European governments defended Israel, and Netanyahu. Israel is now seizing Arab lands in Syria, Gorden, Palestine and Lebanon. Do Israel's immunity and absolute domination initiate the age of Jewish imperialism administered by religious and political fundamentalists like Netanyahu and Trump? Or will it signify the end of the current world order of western double standards and racism towards other civilizations?

Is it Really the Israeli Lobby?

American political scientists John Mearsheimer and Jeffrey Sacks criticize American complicity with the current Israeli genocide in Gaza. Mearsheimer argues that the first Gulf War (1990-91) revealed that Israel was becoming 'a strategic burden' and that 'saying that Israel and

the United States are united by a shared terrorist threat has the causal relationship backwards. Rather, the United States has a terrorism problem in good part because it is so closely allied with Israel, not the other way around' (2007, p. 32). For Mearsheimer, "genocide is a red line", and American, British and German support of Israel's war crimes is specifically "unexplainable" (Mearsheimer 2024). Sacks regards Netanyahu as 'the most dangerous man in the world,' and confirms that 'the war in Gaza could end today if the United States stopped supplying weapons to Israel' (2024). According to Sacks, Netanyahu is the mastermind and cheerleader behind the American wars on Saddam in Iraq, and Al Asad in Syria. Netanyahu also encouraged American military support of Ethiopian to invade Somalia. For Sacks, the Zionist lobby undermines American democracy, and international credibility (2024). After 'the war on terror,' different American administrations develop a misleading concept of security that shows social and national securities in Israel and America as intertwined. The Israeli lobbies in the USA, and many western states, make a significant effort to bend U.S. foreign policy to support, and advance Israel's political interests. Their activities include voting for pro-Israel candidates, funding pro-Israel organizations, and settlements plans, and controlling media outlets. AIPAC and the Conference of Presidents of Major Jewish Organizations are famous Zionist lobbies in the Usa that are run by fundamentalists and hardliners and openly support the Likud party's colonial expansions (Seth 1982; Chomsky 1999; Mearsheimer and Walt

2022). The conflict between the west and the Arabs is a political, and anticolonial conflict. The declared reasons behind the 11 September 2001 attack on the World Trade Center were political including sanctions on Iraq, the unconditional western support of Israeli occupation of Palestine and Southern Lebanon, western support of massacres against Muslims in Somalia, India, and Chechnya, and the strong presence of American troops in Arab countries like Saudi Arabia (Bin Laden 2002). Islamists and terrorists are not only against the west but are also against the majorities of Muslims. They killed civilians in Egypt, Syria, Sudan and all Arab countries to seize power. Their projects of building Islamic States are political projects. Their cultural agenda of Islamizing Arab societies is mainly a political propaganda. The following part of the paper examines political dissent among Arab and Muslim diaspora communities in the West as a form of anti-colonial activism, and anti-political fundamentalism in the west.

Diversity, Citizenship and Freedom of Speech in the Postcolonial, securitized West

Since October 2023, the Palestinian cause became the centre of attention worldwide, particularly in the west. Public spaces, civil organizations and university campuses across the world have become sites of growing protests and activities in support of Palestinians' struggle for the recognition of their rights and the liberation of

their country. Arab and Muslim diaspora communities, western populations, and activists with different backgrounds have gathered and mobilized to object against the Israeli occupation of Palestine, Israeli illegal settlement, the displacement of Palestinians in the occupied territories, and unconditional western military and political support to the apartheid state of Israel, and its genocide in Gaza. Students' movements in the US and Europe launched campaigns to boycott Israeli academic institutions, and to stop investments and businesses in Israel. The global solidarity with Palestinians amid increasing police violence against protesters, particularly minority protesters, and the persistent silencing of freedom of speech in western academia, media, and the public spaces raise serious questions concerning the social security, freedom and politics of coexistence in the cosmopolitan west (Civic Space Report 2024; Saber 2024; Chamas 2023; Bazail-Eimil 2023). By examining political dissent among Muslim diaspora and immigrant communities in western countries from a postcolonial perspective, the paper argues that the concept of diaspora is a political construct. Diaspora can be used by immigrants, the exiled, the displaced, the marginalized as well as those categorized as original natives. In this sense, diaspora not only signifies a spatial disparity between the place where immigrants, for example, live and their homeland, but also denotes cultural, intellectual, emotional, behavioral, historical loss of or parting from or aspiration towards specific values, socioeconomic po-

sitions, powers. Edward Said explains that:

I have felt that most of the alarmist and deeply flawed discussions of Islamic fundamentalism in the West have been intellectually invidious precisely because they have not been compared with Jewish or Christian fundamentalism, both equally prevalent and reprehensible in my own experience of the Middle East. What is usually thought of as a simple issue of judgment against an approved enemy, in double or exile perspective impels a Western intellectual to see a much wider picture, with the requirement now of taking a position as a secularist (or not) on all theocratic tendencies, not just against the conventionally designated ones. (1994 44-5)

Said's double nationality as a Palestinian American enabled him to use his marginal position to 'speak truth to power'. He criticized the double standards in the developed secular world, the political uses of Islam, and Islamophobic ideas in western academia and media, and the construction of "objective truth of the white man's superiority built and maintained by the classical European colonial empires" (p. 22). For Said, the public realm in the multiethnic west is very complex and it is difficult to develop a concept of justice and fairness that "allows for differences between nations and individuals, without at the same time assigning them to hidden hierarchies, preferences, evaluations" (p. 22). Said believed that Islamic, Jewish, and Christian fundamentalisms ex-

ist. The widespread racist, Islamophobic narratives and the dauntless attempts to justify the Gaza genocide by adopting the Israeli story as 'objective truth' compel Arab and Muslim diasporas worldwide to identify with the recurrent othering, enimization and dehumanization of Palestinians and Arabs as terrorists worthy of mass murder and collective punishment. Thousands of Arabs and Muslims living in the west therefore took to the streets to democratically and freely object to the clear political bias and double standards towards Palestinians.

The obvious multiethnic diversity of participants in pro-Palestine protests, and their direct engagement with political decisions in their host western states shocked authorities and decision-makers and disturbed deep-seated power hierarchies in many western countries. Redisciplining these unsettled marginalized minorities and restoring hierarchical orders that define separating lines between genders, classes, ethnicities, and religions become the main duties of western authorities, their police, and the racist groups in these countries. For instance, after 7 October attack, the power, and immunity of the Israeli lobby in America is shown, and Netanyahu is welcomed in the Capitol, when 'US Islamophobia stands out for its enormity' (Mansoor 2024). Arabs, and Muslims in US receive comments to 'go back where you came from,' recalling the widespread global fear and hate crimes that followed 9/11. The Palestinian flag is cut, and removed, students and university staff are arrested

and lose their positions for supporting Palestinian people (Mansoor 2024; Cineas 2023; Salam 2023; Wendling 2023; Human Rights Watch 2024).

Given Israel's contemporary colonial expansion in the Middle East, and their atrocities against Arabs, are Israel and the USA at all democratic when Netanyahu and Trump are accused of corruption and openly utter excluding sexist, racist and fundamentalist opinions? Huntington's ideas on clashes between Islamic and western cultures and civilizations are also perfectly relevant for an understanding of the international and internal divisions regarding the Gaza war, and the political power of Netanyahu and Trump. Huntington states that 'in the politics of civilizations, the peoples and governments of non-Western civilizations no longer remain the objects of history as targets of Western colonialism but join the West as movers and shakers of history' (p. 23). When Huntington points to the heterogenous nature of modern western societies, he hypothesizes that 'as people define their identity in ethnic and religious terms, they are likely to see an 'us' versus 'them' relation existing between themselves and people of different ethnicity or religion' (p. 29). Consequently, civilizational cultural differences are the main reasons behind the fact that 'in Italy, France, and Germany, racism is increasingly open, and political reactions and violence against Arab and Turkish migrants have become more intense and more widespread since 1990' (p. 32). When western countries

benefit from big waves of immigrants from the Middle East, South America, Asia and other parts of the world, and use, and sometimes, exploit them within their economic plans, western authorities and their deep states and circles of power still maintain and disseminate an imperialist culture of hierarchy, *white* racial superiority and western security. Antagonism and racism against immigrants, particularly Muslims who stand for the Islamic civilization, are growing in western countries not because of cultural conflicts as Huntington claims but are due to the widespread political fundamentalisms and populisms.

Huntington essentializes and homogenizes concepts of civilization and identity, ignoring the diversities, and multiplicity of visions within the Islamic and Western civilizations. For example, Islamic countries have different interpretations of Islamic cultural and theological heritages. Likewise, Huntington's argument that conflict will rise because people tend to identify with their ethnicity and religion is controversial. It hints at the conclusion that immigrants, and minorities in America, for example, will never feel integrated, or belong to the American nation, and hence will never feel equal to the natives because they have different values, or religions and consequently will always disagree on policies, human rights, trade and laws. In this sense, western multiethnic, and multicultural communities are made more and more conscious of their original backgrounds, their in-

digenous cultures and their different religions since ‘the European community rests on the shared foundation of European culture and Western Christianity’ (p. 27). Trump uses the same narrative of protecting Western Christianity against enemies. For Trump to ‘make America great again,’ he attacks vulnerable groups such as immigrants. Immediately after winning the presidential election in 2016, violent racist attacks and hate crimes spread in American states against American minorities. Muslims and Arabs, particularly veiled women, were systematically targeted. Arab refugees were prevented from entering the USA (Lajevardi, and Oskooii, 2018; Calfano 2017). Similar fears are on the rise again.

Europe: Why mainly Targeting Arab and Muslim Immigrants and Refugees

During the pro-Brexit propaganda in the UK, like Trump’s election propaganda, poor and lower classes, whether white or nonwhite, imagined a community of pure English people devoid of immigrants, including Europeans, as indicative of social and economic stability and affluence. Eight years after Brexit, British people’s living standards are declining, benefits are being cut, and funding to services is slashed. The British government failed to deal with many urgent economic issues and social tensions but provided Israel with financial and military support. The huge and visible pro-Palestine protests in the UK provoked huge anger towards

Arabs, Muslims, and immigrants in general who chose to exercise their political opinions and to defend their rights of freedom of expression. In July 2024, three girls aged between six and nine were killed at a Taylor Swift-themed dance event for children in the town Southport, England. The attacker was a British-born teenager, but immediately after the incident, fake news spread that the attacker was an Islamist immigrant or asylum seeker. Unprecedented, highly organized, extensive anti-Muslims and anti-immigrants demonstrations spread all over the UK, where mosques and stores owned by Muslims were attacked, violent clashes with Muslims, refugees and non-white people were random and Islamophobic and racist comments dominated social media and were re-used by politicians like Suella Braverman, Nigal Farage, and Robert Jenrick. Anti-Muslims and anti-immigrants in the UK uttered that they want 'their Christian culture again'. The vocality, and visuality of Islamophobic hate in the UK provoke fear and terror among Arab diasporas and immigrants who question their belonging, and identity as citizens in the UK (Abdulla 2024; Pietromar-chi 2024.).

It is quite obvious for first generation migrants to feel diasporic or to miss their homeland where they formed memories and have real ties. However, for second and third generations of immigrants to feel diasporic, and a sense of unbelonging in countries where they are born, and grow up is not justifiable. The fact that the concept

diaspora is indiscriminately and persistently attached to minorities is a political decision to dismiss discussions of serious problems of discriminatory identity politics, socioeconomic inequalities, and political corruption. This is evident in Germany where millions of Arab immigrants feel unstable and insecure as official Islamophobic attitudes are adopted to generalize and villify them as rapists, or terrorists (HRW 2024; Langer 2023; Whittle 2024). In European countries, in Canada, Australia and New Zealand, like in the US, Muslim and Arab diasporas are not only seen as a threat to the cultural homogeneity of the 'original' white natives, and a threat to western identity, or are enemized as defenders of terrorists like Hamas, but also as a threat to what Henry Kissinger called the Westphalian system. Kissinger defines the Westphalian system as 'a multiplicity of political units, none powerful enough to defeat all others, many adhering to contradictory philosophies and internal practices, in search of neutral rules to regulate their conduct and mitigate conflict' (p.3). Kissinger mentions the main advantages of the Westphalian system are that no single claim to truth or universal rule, a balance of power, preference for the practical and ecumenical and distillation of order from multiplicity and restraint (p. 3-4). The rise of pro-Palestine versus pro-Israel protests signifies the emergence of the marginalized in the face of the powerful centres, and exposes the dominance of Jewish, and Christian fundamentalist attitudes in different western contexts. Human rights of equality, justice,

and freedom of speech are challenged. Pro-Palestine protesters expose the hypocrisy of the Westphalian values of multiplicity of opinions, respect of diversities of truths, and objective, practical judgments. Many Muslims and immigrants hold western citizenships, but they are made to feel as outsiders and vulnerable. In this sense, diaspora communities are pushed to live in their separate ghettos. There are legal ramifications as well. Almost all counterterrorism laws indiscriminately target Muslim communities as a threat to national securities of western countries (Choudhury, Fenwick 2011).

Diaspora studies are widely discussed from different perspectives of cultural politics, national consciousness, national identity, civilizational conflicts, myths of homeland, and racialized collectivities (Gilroy 1993; Hall 1994). In *Postcolonial Diasporas*, David Chariandy argues that there is a growing disenchantment with nation-based articulations of postcolonialism due to critical attitudes within feminist, queer, and ethnicity studies, that reexamine concepts of nationalisms, identity, globalization, and diaspora (Chariandy 2016). The Gaza war exposes women in the Middle East and in the West as vulnerable targets of political fundamentalists. Under Trump, women engaged in heated debates on abortion during which traditional, outdated religious and cultural norms, that clearly contradict dominant sexual values in America and the west in general, were used. Different religious texts are selectively used to oppress women and

maintain masculinist superiority over their bodies. Jewish and Christian religious fundamentalists regard the Gaza genocide as a means of achieving religious prophecies. Palestinian women's bodies and their children are specifically sacrificed to reach the goal of Great Israel. About a million Palestinian women are displaced, and 70% of civilians killed in Gaza have been women and children, the Palestinian reproductive force. For long, Palestinian women have been defamed in western and Israeli media as bad mothers of terrorists, and suicide bombers. Famous Jewish rabbis like Eliyahu Mali instructs that the teachings of Halakha, or Jewish laws dictate that vandals in today's war are the children of the previous war whom we kept alive, and in reality, it is the women who produce terrorists, and Israelis should kill 'the future generation (the children of Gaza), and those who produce the future generation (women of Gaza), because there is really no difference. (Shibli 2017; Anadolu 2024; Brettler 2024; Tov 2022). These xenophobic and racist ideas expressed by Jewish rabbis are, however, meaningless if they were not persistently supported by Israeli officials and decision-makers such as Netanyahu, Smotrich and Ben Gvir, Gopstein and others who use the media and call for colonizing Northern Gaza, the annexation of the West Bank, and the building of Great Israel. A recalibration of diaspora studies is therefore required in view of these stark circumstances.

Conclusion:

Amid militarist chaos and the disregard of international laws, Trump's big victory as a dictator can be seen as an attempt to reinforce global order, stability and social security in keeping with colonial hierarchies. The Gaza war exposes Jewish, Muslim and Christian political fundamentalisms as shaping world politics today. Arab protesters in America and in UK, France, Germany and other parts in the west are specifically targeted by police. Fake news is intentionally circulated by western government officials, racist groups and politicized media channels to demonize Muslims and Arabs. Western racists are anxious about their supposedly pure culture being corrupted by minorities, particularly Arabs, thinking that cultural purity brings economic and social equality. Nonetheless, public awareness grows of the fact that billions are spent on weaponizing Ukraine and Israel when common people are struggling with the aftermath of the Covid pandemic, inflation, a global rise of prices of basic goods. Saying so, the paper confirms that colonialist and fundamentalist politics impacted both postcolonial western and colonized countries, albeit at varying degrees and in different forms. The inhuman abuses in Gaza correlate with ongoing socioeconomic, cultural and identity insecurities and fears among Muslims and immigrant communities in the West without any clear solution in sight.

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